

An Analytical Study of Maulana Ubaidullah Sindhi's Basic Trends for Understanding the Holy Qur'an

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ABSTRACT: Maulana Ubaidullah Sindhi (1872-1944) was a prominent Islamic scholar and political thinker from India, known for his revolutionary spirit and his approach towards interpreting the Holy Qur'an in light of social and political issues of his time. His approach to Qur'anic exegesis was both deeply rooted in classical Islamic scholarship while also being progressive, reflecting a unique combination of intellectual tradition and reformist vision. The study of his basic trends in understanding the Qur'an offers valuable insight into how he navigated religious thought in relation to contemporary social, political, and economic challenges. Sindhi believed that the Qur'an should be understood in its historical context, but he also emphasized that its teachings were meant to be applied to contemporary issues. He applied Tafsir bi'l-Ma'thur (traditional exegesis based on narrations) but did not shy away from addressing modern-day political, social, and economic problems. Sindhi saw the Qur'an as a living text with timeless guidance, adaptable to evolving circumstances. A key aspect of Sindhi's interpretation was his focus on socio-political justice, which was particularly influenced by the challenges faced by the Indian subcontinent under colonial rule. He sought to apply Qur'anic principles to address issues like economic inequality, social oppression, and colonial domination, viewing Islam as a transformative force capable of guiding a society towards justice and equality. Ubaidullah Sindhi was a firm believer in the need for reform within the Muslim world. He advocated for a revival of Islamic principles but not in a static or rigid manner. Instead, he argued for a dynamic application of the Qur'an that could cater to modern realities. His reformist tendencies were aimed at both religious and political realms, calling for intellectual awakening and a return to the true spirit of Islam. Sindhi highlighted the need to integrate rational thinking with Qur'anic revelation. He believed that reason ('aql) and revelation (wahy) were not contradictory but rather complementary. This approach allowed him to address contemporary intellectual challenges without compromising on the foundational beliefs of Islam. He interpreted many Qur'anic injunctions in light of their implications for collective welfare. He believed that the Qur'an promotes a vision of society where the welfare of the entire community is prioritized over individual interests. This idea was central to his political thought, which advocated for a society based on principles of collective justice and responsibility. Sindhi's spiritual outlook was influenced by Sufism, particularly the teachings of Shah Waliullah Dehlavi. However, unlike some Sufi interpretations that may have focused more on the esoteric, Sindhi applied spiritual principles to practical socio-political issues, advocating for a balance between the spiritual and material needs of society.

Sindhi's Major Contributions to Qur'anic Exegesis Maulana Ubaidullah Sindhi was heavily influenced by the ideas of Shah Waliullah, who was one of the most prominent reformers in Islamic history. Shah Waliullah's concepts of socio-economic justice, unity of the Muslim *Ummah*, and the balance between spirituality and practical action had a deep impact on Sindhi's Qur'anic interpretation. One of the significant contributions of Sindhi was his focus on the economic teachings of the Qur'an. In the colonial context, where economic exploitation was rampant, Sindhi interpreted Qur'anic verses related to wealth, poverty, and distribution of resources as a mandate for social and economic justice. His ideas prefigured later Islamic socialist thought. Maulana Sindhi's political activism, particularly his involvement in anti-colonial struggles, shaped his Qur'anic interpretation. He viewed the Qur'an as a charter for human liberation, not only in spiritual terms but also in political and economic terms. Sindhi was part of the Deoband School of thought, but his ideas were progressive, aiming to adapt Islamic thought to the colonial and post-colonial realities of the Muslim world. Maulana Ubaidullah Sindhi's progressive and reformist approach to Qur'anic interpretation did not sit well with everyone. Some scholars and religious leaders criticized his interpretations for being too focused on modern political and economic issues, while others felt that he was too revolutionary in his thought, diverging from traditional religious teachings. However, his intellectual courage and his efforts to make Islam relevant to contemporary societal needs won him a great following, particularly among those looking for a synthesis between Islamic tradition and modern reform. Maulana Ubaidullah Sindhi's trends in understanding the Holy Qur'an reveal his deep engagement with the challenges of his time, particularly those posed by colonialism, economic exploitation, and social injustice. His ability to merge traditional Islamic exegesis with modern socio-political concerns makes his work particularly relevant for scholars, activists, and reformers seeking to apply Islamic principles to the contemporary world. His legacy as a scholar who applied the Qur'an to both spiritual and temporal domains continues to inspire Islamic thinkers today.

Keywords: Maulana Ubaidullah Sindhi's, Understanding, Holy Qur'an, Shah Waliullah Dehlavi, Economic, Principles

Introduction

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1. Introduction

There was a lot of change during the 18th century, especially on the Subcontinent. The Industrial Revolution was starting to have an impact on society as the British colonial grip tightened. Aware of these changes, Shah Waliyullah (1703–1762) developed a renaissance philosophy based on the Quran and Hadith that attempted to restore Islamic values to society. Though his thoughts are strewn throughout his writings, the Holy Quran remained his main concern, especially in light of human civilization. Shah Waliyullah's ideas had a great influence on Maulana Ubaidullah Sindhi (1872–1944). He shed more light on the sociological aspects of the Quran. He observed the quick changes in society that

came about as a result of the world wars and the colonial ages while he was living in exile. He committed his life to educating the next generation about Islam's social and political precepts. His four Quranic Tafsirs in different languages show how the teachings of the Quran changed the Arabic civilization of the seventh century. The teachings of the Quran had a significant impact, converting oppressive societies into just ones for almost a millennium.

2. An overview of Maulana Ubaidullah Sindhi's commentary services

Sheikh Al-Hind Maulana Mahmood Hasan revised the Urdu translation of Shah Abdul Qadir Dehlavi and presented it in the current language of the time, which is known as "موضح الفرقان". On the other hand, to transfer Imam Shah Waliullah's principles of exegesis and Quranic thought and philosophy to the students of Darul Uloom Deoband and Aligarh College, the two academic movements of India were created to create harmony among the students of these institutions, to promote Quranic ideas and to dominate religion, the 'Nazarat al-Ma'arif al-Qur'aniya' was created for training on Quranic wisdom. It was established on June 13, 1913 in Delhi, the capital city of United India. Sheikh-ul-Hind Maulana Mahmood Hasan entrusted his trusted disciple Maulana Ubaidullah Sindhi with the responsibility of Nazarat al-Maarif. Where he was involved in this work till 1915.¹

Principles of Studying Holy Quran:

Maulana Ubaidullah Sindhi laid down some basic principles for Quranic study in Nazarat al-Maarif al-Qur'aniyah, which is available in book form. In which Maulana Ubaidullah Sindhi, along with reading the Qur'an, has drawn attention to what should be the collective effects of the study of the Qur'an on the society. Therefore, he presented the principles of studying the Qur'an keeping in mind the wonders of the Qur'an and its effectiveness. In which the basic principles are presented as a sample as follows:

1. The Qur'an calls for prudence and speaks of social formation on it. According to Maulana Sindhi, Muslims are suffering from social degradation despite having a prodigious book like the Quran, which is the main reason for not thinking about the Quran. In this era, what is called or understood as تدبير i.e. understanding is understanding the commentaries of Quran which were written in the context of the specific requirements of their time, which are not even remotely related to the requirements of the 20th century. Verse of Surah Al-Muzamil: *ورتل القرآن ترتيلا*, (And recite the Qur'an with most pleasant pauses.) Maulana Ubaidullah Sindhi says in his interpretation that "Despite the importance and emphasis of reading the Holy Qur'an with understanding, how can Muslims consider the process of reading without thinking and keeping the intellect aside, despite the Qur'an itself describing it as necessary? At what point in time, the idea was created among Muslims that the name of reciting "ح" and "ش" with correct pronunciation without understanding the meaning of the Qur'an is "ترتيل".²

¹ Mansoorpuri, Muhammad Salman (2001), *Asia's Great Revolutionary Leader*, Haji Hanif and Sons, Lahore, p:8,9

² Sindhi, Ubaidullah (2002), *How to Study the Quran?*, Maki Dar al-Kutub, Lahore, p:23

2. It is necessary and compulsory to keep the atmosphere of the age in front of the study of the Qur'an. Maulana Sindhi says that in the basic principles of studying the Qur'an, the understanding of the current time is considering the basic requirements of every age and the conditions of the present time, and awareness of the basic changes taking place in societies, is of great importance. Many verses of the Holy Qur'an show how the Arab society, the first addressee of the Qur'an, was drawn to the conditions of that era. In this context, how can ignoring the important changes of the 20th century and its effects on societies be an appropriate action? In the explanation of Surah Al-Asr, he says that " 'Asr means time, with which there is a concept of passing, that is, passing time, this age is not a fixed thing, but it is changing. The nation that kept adapting itself to the demands of the age rose to prominence. The people who adopted regressiveness either went far behind the times or their culture was lost with the passage of time. And if humanity was completely lost in them, they were wiped out."³

3. When reading the Qur'an, it is inevitable to keep its purpose in mind. As the Qur'an has clarified the objectives of the prophets. Maulana Sindhi says that if a person reads the Holy Qur'an but does not have the purpose of reading it in mind, he will not be able to create its effects in himself, rather he may believe the Qur'an but his actions are against it. The connection of unconsciousness with the Quran or not thinking about it and considering it cannot create any effects and consequences in the society. It is an absolute principle that every action has its own result. The teaching of Holy Qur'an also wants to create its effect in the society.

4. Maulana Ubaidullah Sindhi says that it was only the effect of the teaching of the Holy Quran that in a few years the idolatrous and ignorant people of Arabia became the most God-fearing, the most civilized, the most cultured and the most powerful. The teaching of this Qur'an quickly created such perfect morals in them that if on the one hand, within a few years, the biggest empires of the world had unanimously bowed their heads before them, on the other hand, they were the most god fearing.⁴ The purpose of the Qur'an is to take advantage of historical events and use them to lead a straight path. In Maulana Sindhi's study of the Qur'an, the purpose of the stories of the Qur'an is for conscious people to take advantage of these events in history and make them a source of guidance for themselves. Follow the footsteps of Prophets and pious people and get full success and these are not just anecdotes. The Holy Qur'an has declared the story of Prophet Yusuf (A.S) as احسن القصص meaning the most beautiful story. But it was made into a love story of Prophet Yusuf (A.S) and Zalekha. As a result of which it's political and economic objectives became buried. Maulana Sindhi derives his purpose from the verse (رَبِّ قَدْ آتَيْتَنِي مِنَ الْمَلِكِ) Translation: O my Lord, you have given me a share in the government, and says that not to give up one's goal and to continue working in any situation whether it is freedom or not, is a great lesson. It is the result of this continuous struggle and putting his goal first that Prophet Yusuf (A.S) rose from the level of slavery in a foreign country to the level of a ruler.⁵

³ Sindhi, Ubaidullah (2009), Qur'anic Consciousness of Revolution, Rahimiyah Publications, Lahore, p:592

⁴ Sindhi, Ubaidullah (2002), How to Study the Quran?, Maki Dar al-Kutub, Lahore, p:13

⁵ Sindhi, Ubaidullah (2009), Qur'anic Consciousness of Revolution, Rahimiyah Publications, Lahore, p:699

5. Quranic terminologies and words have meaning in themselves, which must be understood in the correct context. This was the tendency of Maulana Sindhi was that it is necessary to keep the original Qur'an in view, by merely keeping in view translations or interpretations, distance is created from the vastness of the words of the Qur'an. Its biggest loss was that misconceptions were prevalent. Another disadvantage is that more attention is focused on what the commentator has emphasized, leaving important parts of the Qur'an neglected. Thus, instead of the original book being in front, if other things remain in view, then the reality of the Quran, its original teaching will not be revealed and the universality of the Quran will go into the background. For example, the meaning of "supplication" is the concept of asking Allah without doing anything and imagining that Allah will grant it automatically. As if prayer has become the name of inaction. Maulana Sindhi says in the commentary of the verse of Surah Fatiha (اهدنا الصراط المستقيم) that the meaning of dua should be the expression of the intention that we make in our hearts, that is, that we will act on this path. We will spend all our strength. But we know that there will be obstacles in this way, at that time we will ask our Lord, the Most Merciful, the All-Mighty, to help us remove these obstacles from our path. Until we succeed in our goal. In this sense, dua is the name of asking for help to remove the obstacles faced during the process.⁶

3. A study of collective, social and civil concepts in Maulana Sindhi's Tafsir

To clarify the style of Tafseer of Maulana Ubaidullah Sindhi, the tafsir of selected verses will be explained below:

The purpose of prophecy is the completion of human society:

Maulana Ubaidullah Sindhi, while commenting on the first verse of Surah al-Fatiha, defines the meaning of Al-Alamin and states that Al-Alamin means nations and states. Al-Alamin is applied to everyone except Allah and it is also applied to the human race among the creatures. As it is in the verse, "أني فضلتكم علي العالمين"⁷ that is, he gave superiority to the Qur'anic community over the existing nations of the time. Surah Al-Fatiha is the summary of the Great Quran, which was revealed to Prophet Muhammad PBUH and the subject of prophethood is human collectivity. Therefore, these words in the Holy Quran are related to humanity. The mention of the things of the earth, sky and the universe or the mention of jinn, angels, heaven and hell is in the context of this collective humanity. The main goal is the completion of the humanity. The purpose of Prophet Muhammad PBUH is for all nations to obey the general movement under the system of human nature.⁸

After that, while summarizing, he says that (الحمد لله رب العالمين) means the world order that Allah, Lord of the Worlds has established, which exists in different nations, there is no flaw in its system. This system is in accordance with human nature. On the other hand, to think of a system that would be better than this is nothing but stupidity. He who has such a negative thought in his mind should put his full strength into three tasks.

1. In understanding this system

⁶ Ibid, p:77

⁷ Quran (Al-Baqrah:47)

⁸ Ibn Manzur, Jamal al-Din Muhammad bin Makram (1998), Lisan al-Arab, Dar Sader, Beirut, Vol:12, p:420-421

2. In establishing this system on human nature.
3. In not being against the nature of this system.

But such an imaginative mind will be humbled to establish a good system. Some scholars have said that the no system can be better than the system established by Allah. That is, this sentence of Surah Fatiha is claiming that it is impossible to have a system like this.⁹

Expansion in the meaning of the Lord of Nations (رب الأقاليم):

Any human being personally recognizes Allah as his God. When he looks at the world, he will naturally consider his Lord as Lord of the Worlds, meaning Lord of all Nations. By this, the introduction of the Lord in this individual will not only be associated with his self, but the concept of being the Lord of the entire human race will emerge and create expansion in his mind and psyche. Allah is not the Lord of this individual, his family, his tribe or his nation, but He is the Lord of all the nations of the world. And He will gradually bring all nations to the level of evolution which He aims to create. Thus, the mind of the one who accepts this theory will be freed from tribal, regional and national prejudices and will turn towards the service of humanity. Along with his relationship with his Lord, he will be attracted towards new goals of social evolution by becoming a friend of humanity.¹⁰

Meaning and requirement of servitude:

Maulana Sindhi says in the fourth verse of Surah al-Fatihah in Tafsir Ilqa al-Manan (تفسير لقاء المنان) that a person confesses that he worships only Allah in the act of worship in the verse اياك نعبد. Because the honor of man is in the service of Allah. This existence and human greatness are entrusted to him. There is no worship of anyone but Allah. Nor is there any further development of man. When a man rejects all other servitudes, and he makes up his mind that other objects are of no help to him, he does not seek help from anyone else. If he asks for help from someone else, he will become his slave. It is permissible for one person to cooperate with another. Because, under the requirement of war of mutual necessity, someone does our work, then we come to his help. There is no slavery in this two-way process. Servant hood is one-sided that it is only sought from Allah. The mind-set of asking someone else creates slavery. With the right mind-set of servitude, man thrives. While maintaining this freedom, a person should build a house, build a city, build a country, or become a Caliph of a country.¹¹

Divine grace refers to knowledge and government:

Maulana Sindhi says in Tafsir Al-Maqam Al-Mahmoud in Surah Al-Baqarah 2:40 that Allah's blessings mean knowledge and government. Knowledge is necessary for the development of the mind, and government is necessary for the establishment of religion. Allah Almighty gave the People Israel the government and the government was in their possession as long as they obeyed the divine law. And when they became

⁹ Ibid

¹⁰ Sindhi, Ubaidullah (2009), Qur'anic Consciousness of Revolution, Rahimiyah Publications, Lahore, p:113

¹¹ Sindhi, Ubaidullah (1994), Sindhi Tafsir, Shah Waliullah Academy, Hyderabad, Vol:1, p:3

disobedient, the government was taken away from them and given instead to the law-abiding people, the Muslims. The condition of the Arabs improved by following this Qur'an. These verses of Holy Qur'an are interesting that before Islam, many civilized and cultured people have passed in the world. Like the Jews and Christians, but their culture is a ruined thing that cannot be practiced now, nor can it be practiced at this time. At this time, the world needs another complete law that has been promised. In the present age, no one can benefit from the first books, i.e. Torah, Psalms, and the Gospel, unless he uses the teachings of the Holy Qur'an. Without the Qur'an, no government can be established in this age. The guarantor of the needs of the present age is also the Qur'an. Therefore, **عهد الله** means the Book of Allah. Through this Book of Allah, Allah Almighty makes a contract with the nations that this book is given to you and you should follow all its commands fully. The result of following this will be that you will be given great governments in this world and paradise in the hereafter. ¹²

4. Evolution of civilized life

Maulana Sindhi in verse 60 of Surah al-Baqarah in Tafsir al-Maqam, Sindhi says that the process of water distribution in this verse shows that the Israelites are moving from Bedouin life to civilized life. Twelve springs were released for them and each tribe is drawing water from its own spring. Similarly in urban life where resources are distributed, there are neighbour hoods in the city, each neighborhood has separate population and wells.¹³

Halal sustenance and justice are the basic requirements of human society:

In Tafsir al-Maqam al-Mahmud, in the commentary of verse 168 of Surah Al-Baqarah, Sindhi says that in this verse, humans are ordered to earn lawful and pure sustenance, this is the foundation of human dignity and civilization. Earning halal then eating well cooked food. The cruel people are the brothers of the devil. The rules and regulations made by them are satanic, which will teach usury, the ways of oppression and the schemes of robbery. Humanity is the name of collectivism. For the establishment of collectivism, it is necessary that business is halal and fair. If there is injustice, then civilization deteriorates, as a result of which the urban management falls apart. Desolation comes in its place and humanity becomes a victim of suffering. So this is the devil's work and the evil and deceitful people are your visible enemies. They want to destroy your wealth, your honor, your religion. ¹⁴

Reasons for differences among nations:

Maulana Sindhi says in Tafsir Ilham al-Rahman in verse 213 of Surah Al-Baqarah that all human beings are created in the same way. The basic principles of their rural and urban life are of the same level. International prophets have been coming for their development. They were given international law to refer to in case of any mutual dispute and the decision was preserved. Prophets not only told them the basic rules of international

¹² Sindhi, Ubaidullah (n.d.), Mawlana, Alqa al-Manan fi Tafsir al-Quran, Jamia Ishaat al-Uloom, Chishtian, p:3

¹³ Sindhi, Ubaidullah (1997), Tafsir al-Maqam al-Mahmud, Maki Dar al-Kutub, Lahore, p:257

¹⁴ Ibid, p:333

affairs but also explained them well. But they fought with each other only for personal and their limited national benefit. Maulana Sindhi says that:¹⁵

“If the ignorant people fought, there would have been no harm, but the injustice was that those scholars and jurists who knew this book, they themselves disagreed in the interpretation of this book. The reason for this disagreement was based on personal interest, and they did not agree about the administration of the law. One group said that this international law would be successful in so and so way and the other group said that it would be successful in such and such way. If there was such a difference, then both of them would have reached a unified point of view to make it successful, but they only fought for their personal interest and each of them interpreted the book in such a way that it would benefit them personally. In the same way, the parties fought with each other and put such a difference in the international law.”

Now the situation is that the straight path is not visible. But Prophet Muhammad PBUH gave international law in the form of the Qur'an which resolves all their differences. This is the direct and general way. By taking the individual path, the nation is ultimately doomed. When a nation subjugates other nations for its own profit, the other nation makes such an effort to gain its independence that it destroys its national government. In this verse, Muslims were explained the purpose of sending the Messenger and the need for the book. Muslims were told that you too will be destroyed if you disagree in your book. It also happened when each sect made interpretations based on personal motives for their group purposes that now the other does not give a straight path in it. Now, if a sensible person studies the Qur'an without these commentaries, he will understand it. Otherwise, it has been made a place of fighting in Tafsir.¹⁶

Contract of marriage and contract of governance:

In Tafsir al-Qa'i al-Manan, verses 227-226 of Surah Al-Baqarah, Sindhi says that everyone in the house belongs to one law. Every person has a status in law. They have a duty to fulfil. No one is allowed to dispose of more than the right of another. A man takes an oath not to go near a woman. This would mean that he has set a period of four months to consider the future of his household affairs. It is absolutely not allowed for him to dispose of the rights of a woman and keep her in the house for the rest of her life. A man swears that he will not go near a woman. An oath is a jurisprudential matter. In the mutual relationship of husband and wife, such an oath that has no determination is not accepted by the Qur'an, because these purposes will end the marriage. If a matter is settled by the mutual consent of the parties that they will not have intercourse, it is not a matter of concern. This is not the only purpose of marriage and there are other benefits as well.¹⁷

The man has been made the ruler in the house. As a ruler, his opinion is more important. He uses his sovereign judgment to decide not to approach the woman. It is as if the man moves towards ending his sovereignty. Quranic law gives him the right to think about it for four months. After four months, the man comes to the conclusion that there is no

¹⁵ Ibid, p:368-369

¹⁶ Ibid

¹⁷ Sindhi, Ubaidullah (1994), Sindhi Tafsir, Shah Waliullah Academy, Hyderabad, Vol:1, p:274-275

need to maintain a relationship with this woman. So this decision of his, which was an oath, will be considered as divorce, that is the man has separated from his wife. Or after thinking for four months, he sees the harm in separating from the woman and turns back, i.e. breaks his oath, then Allah will forgive his mistake if they remain as husband and wife. If the common people know their rights, no ruler will be able to oppress them. But it started to be taught among Muslims that if the king does injustice, be patient. Allah will reward patience. Modern people do not like to fight with the ruler. Because now the styles of governance have changed and the tenure of the rulers has been determined, one goes and another good ruler comes. There is no such teaching in Islam that subjects should bow down to a tyrannical king. The purpose of appointing the king is to establish justice among the people. If he does not fulfil this right, he will be informed that he must correct his behaviour within such a period, otherwise the right to rule will be revoked. Now the expediency requirement is also that a ruler should be made for a fixed period of time.¹⁸

The need to protect government secrets:

Maulana Sindhi says in Tafsir al-Maqam al-Humood, verse 28 of Surah Aale Imran, that when Muslims get government, they will also get government secrets. Which need to be protected. When relations are established with enemies for any social or economic matter, there is a fear that they will become aware of these secrets, and harm the Muslim government. So friendship with infidels is prohibited. Maulana Sindhi says that:

"Those who are not enemies in moral matters are friends. And those who are friends are not enemies, but in matters of government those who are not friends are enemies, even those who are neutral are also enemies. Only those people who have complete trust will be involved in the government."¹⁹

Muslims with this view will fulfill their responsibility keeping in mind the collective interests and will be punished in case of any negligence. This government of Muslims will perform its duties with full honesty.

Ubaidullah Sindhi's Tafsir style:

Maulana Ubaidullah Sindhi's Tafsir text is a type of speculator style. Imam Shah Waliullah states in Usul Tafsir that an important problem is the derivation of rulings from the verses of the Qur'an. One of the Qur'anic sciences is science of reliability, which is a form of inference. Which was declared correct by Prophet PBUH so that another way would be opened in understanding these sciences and reaching their core. It has been said about the Holy Quran that:

“ لكل آية منها ظهير وبطن ، ولكل حد مطلع ”²⁰

Translation: “Each verse of the Qur'an has an apparent and an inner meaning, and every interdiction has a source of reference”.

¹⁸ Ibid

¹⁹ Sindhi, Ubaidullah (1997), Tafsir al-Maqam al-Mahmud, Maki Dar al-Kutub, Lahore, p:246,247

²⁰ Abu Abdullah, Muhammad bin Abdullah (n.d.), Mishkat al-Masabih, Kitab-ul-'Ilm, No:211

Therefore, the apparent of the verses of the Holy Qur'an is what the words of the verse indicate, and what is commonly called the meaning, the inner of all verses is different. And the essence of the verses of commands is to find out those commands which are hidden and not revealed by the words of the verses, through the context of the verse. In the context of this conversation, Maulana Ubaidullah Sindhi's style is also the same that he infers another order from the Quranic interpretation. For this he refers to Quran and Hadith. He does not deviate in any way from the wisdom and essence of the orders. All the exegetical discussions of Maulana Sindhi show the practical system of the Qur'an. From which the Quranic teachings, instead of being limited to academic discussions, attract the practical system of formation of all stages of the national and international level. Thus a social resource comes before us.²¹

5. Summary

Quran is the last book of Almighty Allah on which Prophet Muhammad PBUH built a society and his party. This era of Khair al-Qur'on (The best of times) became a source of guidance for future humans. Human society is changing. When the conditions of the times change, human societies are faced with the need of guidance according to the requirements of the era.

From the Holy Qur'an, its interpretation and interpretation continued in every era for guidance, and various methods came into existence. Among them, Tafsir Bil mathur, Tafsir Bil Ra'yi were the main methods. Along with this, the literary, jurisprudential, verbal, symbolic, intellectual and scientific aspects that come under Tafsir Bil Ra'yi are prominent.

In the eighteenth century, a great change took place in the world. Scientific evolution and the invention of the machine had profound effects on the society. Imam Shah Waliullah formulated a philosophy on religious sciences during this period. Ubaidullah Sindhi translated the Quran into Persian. Shah Waliullah and other intellects provided translation and commentary of the Qur'anic sciences in Urdu and made the study of the sciences of Quran easier.

In the 19th century Muslim rule declined and the European nations dominated. In the 20th century, the Muslim world system completely broke down and with it the nation-state system evolved and the nation-democratic era began.

In view of these challenges of the twentieth century, Sheikh Al-Hind Maulana Mahmood Hasan created Nazrah Al-Maarif Al-Qur'an to make use of Shah Wali Ullah's sciences. In which students of colleges and madrasas were brought together on a single platform. He appointed his disciple Maulana Ubaidullah Sindhi as its chief administrator.

Maulana Ubaidullah Sindhi presented the principles of studying the Qur'an and explained the wisdom of the Qur'an, its compatibility with the needs of the age, the purposes of the Qur'an and the comprehensiveness of the words of the Qur'an. Maulana Ubaidullah Sindhi gave Quranic lessons to his students which he wrote down. From which four interpretations were introduced in Arabic Sindhi and Urdu. Among them are Tafsir Al-

²¹ Dehlavi, Shah Waliullah (1980), Al-Fawz al-Kabir, Maktabah Burhan, Urdu Bazar, p:153

ul-Rahman (Arabic), Al-Qa Al-Manan fi Tafsir al-Qur'an (Sindhi), Tafsir al-Maqam al-Mahmoud (Urdu) and Qur'anic Consciousness in Revolution (Urdu).

Maulana Ubaidullah Sindhi was of the view that on the basis of Qur'anic teachings, Khair al-Quron was formed, which lasted in one form or another for a thousand years. In the same way, the Qur'an wants to create its own society in every era. The social structure of the 20th century must also be built on the Holy Qur'an.

Maulana Ubaidullah Sindhi clearly explains the social structure of the 20th century keeping in view the Quranic interpretations. The main point of his interpretation is the guidance of human society. He explains the formation of the state by interpretation of family affairs, orders of worship. He clarifies the Qur'anic principles of social formation by discussing the Qur'an, Hadith, jurisprudence and literary aspects.

He discusses his own era, which is why his interpretation includes science, machines, democracy, and the dominance of European nations and the discourse of independence from them. It also makes clear what will be characteristics of the formation of Quranic society in this modern era.

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